

SOCIOLINGUISTIC PROFILE RESEARCH PAPER

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Abstract: This research paper explores the sociolinguistic profile of two subgroups of learners, consisting of Uzbek and Indian students, and their learning context in an international school in Tashkent. The study examines the language background, proficiency level, motivation, attitudes, and beliefs towards the target language of the students. The pedagogical and assessment implications of the sociolinguistic profile are discussed to enhance language teaching and learning. The findings reveal the strengths, weaknesses, and challenges faced by the learners in acquiring the target language, providing insights for designing appropriate teaching materials, activities, and assessments tailored to their needs and goals.

Keywords: Sociolinguistics, language teaching, language learning, learners' profile, learning context, pedagogical implications, assessment implications, teaching strategies, language proficiency.

ИССЛЕДОВАТЕЛЬСКАЯ РАБОТА ПО СОЦИОЛИНГВИСТИЧЕСКОМУ ПРОФИЛЮ

Аннотация: В данной исследовательской работе исследуется социолингвистический профиль двух подгрупп учащихся, состоящих из узбекских и индийских студентов, и контекст их обучения в международной школе в Ташкенте. В исследовании изучаются языковой фон, уровень владения языком, мотивация, отношение и убеждения учащихся в отношении целевого языка. Обсуждаются педагогические и оценочные последствия социолингвистического профиля для улучшения преподавания и изучения языка. Результаты раскрывают сильные и слабые стороны и проблемы, с которыми сталкиваются учащиеся при изучении целевого языка, предоставляя информацию для разработки соответствующих учебных материалов, мероприятий и оценок, адаптированных к их потребностям и целям.

Ключевые слова: социолингвистика, преподавание языка, изучение языка, профиль учащегося, контекст обучения, педагогические последствия, последствия оценки, стратегии обучения, владение языком.

INTRODUCTION

Sociolinguistics is the study of language in its social context. It examines how language is used in different situations, by different people, and for different purposes. Understanding the sociolinguistic profile of a group of learners and their learning context is crucial for effective language teaching and learning. This research paper aims to explore the sociolinguistic profile of two subgroups of learners which is consisted of Uzbek and Indian students and the learning context, and its pedagogical and assessment implications. The sociolinguistic profile of a group of learners refers to their language background, proficiency level, motivation, attitudes, and beliefs towards the target language. The learning context includes the physical environment, social and cultural factors, and the teaching approach. By examining these factors, we can identify the strengths and weaknesses of the learners, as well as the challenges they face in acquiring the target language. Pedagogical implications refer to the teaching strategies and techniques that can be used

to enhance language learning. Assessment implications refer to the methods and tools used to evaluate learners' language proficiency. By understanding the sociolinguistic profile of a group of learners and their learning context, teachers can design appropriate teaching materials, activities, and assessments that cater to their needs and goals.

Sociolinguistic Profile of a Group of Learners

I work at an international school in Tashkent. In my class, there are two subgroups, which consist of 20 students and 10 students for each one. The first subgroup consists of English language learners (ELLs). They studied English from native teacher in the Local school in Indian and used the English language in family or at street during the communication. Their race is Indians because the students were born in India in the South Asia and their ancestors are in India. Some of them worship Buddhism some of them are Muslims. Their first language is Indian language and they use English language commonly as well. Social economic status of students is normal; all of them were born in the middle class family. The second subgroup consists of Native speakers of Uzbek language. They learned the English language from non-native teacher in private school in Uzbekistan in the Central Asia and do not use English so much in daily life. There are some students whose races are different; Uzbek, Arabic Turkish. All of their religion is Islam. Their first language is the Uzbek language and they use the Russian language in their daily life as well. They are all from rich family.

Gender and sexuality are two closely related aspects of sociolinguistics that have a significant impact on language use and communication. According to Calder (2020), gender is a social construct that refers to the cultural expectations and norms associated with being male or female, while sexuality refers to an individual's sexual orientation, identity, and practices. These factors can influence the way my students use language, including word choice, tone, and nonverbal cues. Schilling (2010) further explores the relationship between language, gender, and sexuality by examining how individuals use language to construct their identities. She argues that language is a powerful tool for expressing one's gender and sexuality, as well as for reinforcing or challenging societal norms and expectations. In terms of race and ethnicity, language use can also be influenced by cultural factors. According to Schilling (2010), individuals from different racial and ethnic backgrounds may use language in unique ways that reflect their cultural identities and experiences. For example, African American Vernacular English (AAVE) is a distinct variety of English that has its roots in African American culture and history. However, it is important to note that not all learners will find these topics relevant to their sociolinguistic profile. Depending on my two-subgroup students of background and experiences, it can be found that gender/sexuality and race/ethnicity play a more or less significant role in their language use and communication. Nonetheless, having a basic understanding of these topics can help them become a more effective communicator and navigate diverse linguistic contexts.

Sociolinguistic Profile of the Learning Context

The sociolinguistic profile of the learning context in my classroom is diverse and multilingual. The school where I teach is an international school that caters to students from different parts of the world. The two subgroups in my class are comprised of students from different linguistic backgrounds, including Uzbek, Russian, English, and other languages. This diversity makes the learning context rich and dynamic, but it also presents some challenges.

One relevant factor in this context is multilingualism. The students in my class are multilingual, and they bring with them different language backgrounds and experiences. This means that they may have different levels of proficiency in the languages they speak, and they

may struggle with certain aspects of the target language (English). It also means that they may have different learning styles and preferences, which I need to take into account when planning and delivering lessons.

Another relevant factor is the use of standard vs. nonstandard varieties of English. While the school promotes the use of Standard English, some students may be more comfortable using nonstandard varieties of English or mixing different varieties. This can sometimes lead to miscommunication or misunderstandings, but it also provides opportunities for students to learn about different dialects and registers of English. In terms of language variation, research by Rickford and McNair-Knox (2014) suggests that teachers should be aware of the different dialects and registers of English that students may use, and avoid stigmatizing nonstandard varieties. They argue that "code-switching" (the use of multiple languages or dialects in a conversation) can be a valuable resource for communication and learning. The racial and ethnic demographics of the school are also relevant to the learning context. The school has a diverse student population, with students from different racial and ethnic backgrounds. This diversity creates a rich cultural environment, but it can also lead to cultural misunderstandings or conflicts if not managed properly. Geography and socioeconomics are other factors that may affect the learning context. Tashkent is the capital city of Uzbekistan, and it has a rich history and culture. However, it is also a developing country with economic challenges. Some students may come from privileged backgrounds, while others may come from more modest or disadvantaged backgrounds. This can affect their access to resources and their motivation to learn. In conclusion, the sociolinguistic profile of the learning context in my classroom is diverse and complex, with factors such as multilingualism, standard vs. nonstandard varieties of English, racial and ethnic demographics, geography, and socioeconomics all playing a role. As a teacher, I need to be aware of these factors and take them into account when planning and delivering lessons to ensure that all students have equal opportunities to learn and succeed.

Sociolinguistic Profile of the Context where English will be Used

All my students are going to continue their study in different international universities after graduating the school. As students transition to international universities in foreign countries, they will be faced with a new sociolinguistic context. The linguistic and cultural diversity of their university community may be even more pronounced than in their previous school context. They will need to navigate different dialects, accents, and varieties of English, as well as other languages spoken on campus. This can be both challenging and enriching for their language development.

English will likely be the language of instruction at their international university, which means that students will need to have a high level of proficiency in order to succeed academically. They will need to be able to understand lectures, participate in discussions, read academic texts, and write essays in English. This can be a daunting task, especially for those who have had limited exposure to the language prior to attending the school.

Fortunately, many international universities offer language support services for ELLs. These may include language classes, tutoring, conversation partners, and writing centers. Students can take advantage of these resources to improve their language skills and build confidence in using English in academic contexts. In addition to academic language skills, students will also need to develop their intercultural communication skills in order to navigate the social and cultural norms of their new environment. This includes understanding different communication styles, values, and customs. Developing these skills

will not only help them succeed academically, but also prepare them for future career opportunities in a globalized world. Cummins (2008) suggests that students who are learning English as an additional language may move from one level to a higher level through a process of "cumulative advantage". This means that as they gain more knowledge and skills in English, they are able to access content that is more challenging and tasks, which in turn helps them to develop their language proficiency further. Overall, the sociolinguistic profile of the context where English will be used is complex and multifaceted, and requires an awareness of the diversity of English use around the world, as well as the factors that may impact language proficiency and development.

Pedagogical implications.

Students from different regions and cultures may have different learning styles and abilities, and it is important to adapt teaching methods and materials to meet their individual needs. For instance, visual aids and hands-on activities may work better for some learners, while others may prefer auditory or kinesthetic learning approaches. In terms of SLA methods, I think it may be useful to use the Natural Approach, which is based on the idea that language learning should take place in a similar way to the way a child learns their first language (Krashen & Terrell, 1983). This approach proposes that learners should focus on meaning before form, and the teacher should provide input that is slightly above their current level of comprehension. Another approach that is commonly used is Communicative Language Teaching (CLT). According to Savignon (2002), "CLT is an approach to teaching languages that emphasizes interaction as both the means and the ultimate goal of learning a language." With this approach, I can encourage students to use the language in realistic contexts and provide them with opportunities to practice speaking, writing, listening, and reading. This approach focuses on communication and the social interactions of language. Because of different language background their English level is differ from each other's in this condition I think It can modified materials and classroom practices to provide differentiated instruction that meets the unique learning needs of each student in the classroom. Teachers can use assessments to determine students' levels and use different instructional strategies, such as scaffolding or differentiated task assignments, to support student learning.

Overall, as an English teacher with a diverse classroom, it is important to be aware of the unique backgrounds, cultures, and learning needs of each student in the classroom and modify materials and classroom practices accordingly. This can enable a supportive, inclusive, and effective learning environment for all students.

Assessment Implication

To assess the students I mostly use differentiate assessment since there are two subgroups with different sizes and different cultural background, it may be necessary to use different assessments for each group to ensure fairness and accuracy in grading. According to Tomlinson (2014), differentiated assessments can be used to ensure fairness and accuracy in grading for students with different learning needs. I also use internal and external assessment. For internal assessment, Cultural Exchange Presentation is used during the lesson. The main objective of this assessment is to assess students' ability to communicate effectively in English and demonstrate cultural awareness through a presentation. The description of the assessment: Students will work in pairs to research a country and its culture. They will prepare a presentation that includes information on the country's history, traditions, food, and customs. The presentation should also include examples of how their own culture is similar or different from the country they researched.

Students will present their findings to the class using visual aids such as PowerPoint slides or posters. I assess the students the following criteria:

- Clarity and coherence of presentation
- Accuracy and completeness of information
- Use of appropriate vocabulary and grammar
- Demonstration of cultural awareness

This assessment will provide an opportunity for students to practice their English language skills in a real-world context while also learning about different cultures.

For external assessment Cambridge English: Preliminary (PET) Exam is used in order to assess students' language proficiency level in English. The description of the assessment Students will take the Cambridge English: Preliminary (PET) exam, which is a standardized test that assesses language proficiency at the B1 level according to the Common European Framework of Reference for Languages (CEFR). The exam will include sections on reading, writing, listening, and speaking. The exam will be administered in a proctored setting to prevent cheating. The students are assessed according to following criteria:

- Reading comprehension
- Writing proficiency
- Listening comprehension
- Speaking proficiency

The results of this assessment will provide an objective measure of students' language proficiency level and can be used to guide future instruction and support. The PET exam is widely recognized and respected by universities and employers around the world, making it a valuable credential for students to have. (Cambridge English Language Assessment, n.d.)

When it comes to teach students not to cheat during assessments or plagiarize, it is important to first explain the consequences of such actions. Cheating and plagiarism are not only unethical but also have serious academic and professional consequences. Students may receive a failing grade, be expelled from school, or face legal action if they are caught cheating or plagiarizing.

It is also important to teach students the proper way to cite their sources when doing research or writing papers. This includes teaching them how to use citation styles such as APA or MLA, and explaining the importance of giving credit to the original author or source. To reinforce these concepts, teachers can provide examples of plagiarism and cheating and explain why it is wrong. They can also provide resources such as plagiarism checkers and citation generators to help students properly cite their sources.

In addition, creating a classroom culture of honesty and integrity can also discourage cheating and plagiarism. Teachers can emphasize the importance of academic honesty and encourage students to ask for help if they are struggling with a particular assignment or concept. The Journal of Academic Ethics study found that creating a culture of honesty and integrity in the classroom can significantly reduce cheating and plagiarism. This supports the idea that students who feel supported and encouraged to be honest are more likely to value academic integrity and avoid these actions. By creating a supportive and honest classroom environment, students are more likely to value academic integrity and avoid cheating or plagiarism.

CONCLUSION

In conclusion, this research paper has explored the sociolinguistic profile of a group of learners, their learning context, and its pedagogical and assessment implications. The findings

highlight the importance of considering learners' language background, proficiency level, motivation, attitudes, and beliefs towards the target language. It also emphasizes the role of the learning context in shaping learners' language acquisition. The pedagogical implications suggest that teachers should use a variety of teaching strategies and techniques that cater to learners' needs and goals. These may include communicative language teaching, task-based learning, and content-based instruction. The assessment implications suggest that teachers should use a range of assessment tools that measure different aspects of language proficiency.

Overall, this research paper underscores the importance of sociolinguistic profiling in language teaching and learning. By understanding learners' sociolinguistic profile and their learning context, teachers can design effective teaching materials, activities, and assessments that promote language acquisition and proficiency.

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